

An IoT M2M Architecture for BMS Using Multiple Connectivity Technologies: A Practical Approach

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Abstract—Europe’s latest energy framework aims to decrease energy consumption and mitigate carbon dioxide emissions while regulating thermal comfort for the occupants through Home energy management systems (HEMSs) or Building Management Systems (BMSs). In this paper, a practical approach for IoT interconnecting sensors and actuators to a BMS is presented. The architecture is based on a centric BMS, communicating with numerous IoT gateways, while various widely used communication protocols are interlinked to the gateway networks, facilitating the system’s interoperability and integration. Moreover, energy saving actions may be handled by the proposed system and specific controls may be sent by the BMS to the actuators to perform automatic energy saving commands. During the experiments, various tests were deployed to verify the system’s perpetual operation.

Index Terms—IoT, connectivity protocols, centric BMS system, gateway, monitoring, controlling, actuators, sensors

I. INTRODUCTION

Until 2016, almost 5 billion of devices were connected to the Internet of Things (IoT) network, nowadays it is estimated that the connected devices are almost 31 billion. Therefore, it is of ultimate importance to have a secure IoT architecture that can be easily deployed and applied even for large-scale networks. There are many IoT types tailored to

various sectors: commercial IoT (e.g., vehicle-to-vehicle V2V communication), consumer IoT (e.g., voice aid for elderly people), Infrastructure IoT (e.g., smart cities), IoT (e.g., smart agriculture), and Military Things (e.g., robots for surveillance) [1]. Overall, regardless the type of each IoT, each network must provide interoperability and feasibility.

The interoperability of the IoT is based on the capability of interconnection of various sensors, devices, and the internet [2]. As a result, there is a plethora of technologies, protocols and methodologies related to connectivity. Therefore, IoT architectures that support many connection-related technologies are of crucial importance. Moreover, there are many IoT architectures with various requirements based on the IoT use-case they are deployed to [3]. Each IoT application is implemented based on the data rate, data latency, network coverage and energy efficiency [2].

The IoT technologies are evolving fast, but old ones still exist, therefore an IoT architecture must support both old and new ones [2]. Some examples include traditional cellular connectivity technologies like EDGE (2G), HSPA (3G), LTE (4G) [4] and Low Power Wide Area (LPWA) technologies for IoT [5]. The LPWA are low-power and low-cost technologies that are capable of covering a wide area network [6]. The most

widely used LPWA are LoRa and Sigfox [6].

Furthermore, multiple connectivity technologies exist for shorter area cover. Short-area connectivity technologies are implemented mostly for HEMS and Building Energy Management Systems (BEMSs) to cover areas up to 100 meters [7]. The most widely used short-area technologies are Bluetooth and Wireless-Fidelity (Wi-Fi) [8]. Moreover, nowadays other technologies like Thread, WirelessHART [9], Z-Wave, Mod-Bus and Zigbee [10] are mostly used in HEMS and BEMS.

As a result, a low-cost IoT architecture supporting multiple connectivity technologies is of key importance. The objective of this paper is to suggest a method for deploying a low-cost machine-to-machine (M2M) centric architecture that supports multiple protocols. Even though there is a plethora of suggested IoT architectures in the literature, this paper aims to be a practical basis to build an IoT network. Within this context, the rest of the paper is structured as follows: in Section II, the methodology of the proposed IoT network is presented and analyzed. Section, III presents the experimental results while conclusions are drawn in the last section.

II. IOT M2M ARCHITECTURE

A. Architecture

The suggested Machine-to-Machine (M2M) system utilizes a modular and layered architecture to increase the system’s overall robustness. In Fig.1 the overall architecture concept of a gateway entity is presented.

Fig. 1. IoT to BMS conceptual architecture

Each gateway is capable of covering a room, house, or building depending on the sensor topology, the number of sensors, and the IoT use-case. Each gateway’s data are stored separately in the BMS database. In this paper’s experiments, each gateway is a Raspberry Pi 4 (RPi) [11] with all the protocols connected through USB sticks that support serial or wireless communication technologies as depicted in Fig. 2. The rest of the architecture is presented for a single gateway.

Each gateway utilizes its own MQTT broker [12]. The broker is used by all the sub-modules’ services to redirect

Fig. 2. Gateway and USB-sticks for various protocols

the data streams to the service in charge of posting them to the BMS server. The use of a local broker for each gateway solves many networking problems that may arise. The gateway can be connected to the internet without the use of static IP while its IP is not stored or used by the system. Additionally, by using the MQTT protocol, different modules of the system can be coded in various programming languages as long as they are compatible with MQTT and post their data to the predefined topics. Each protocol’s software is linked to a Linux service which monitors its network state, manages the sensor data streams, and publishes the data to the gateway’s MQTT broker under predefined and mapped topics.

The "Mqtt2Bms" (Fig. 1) service subscribes to all the topics in the broker using the same predefined mappings, gathers all available data, and periodically posts them to the BMS server’s API.

This type of architecture allows the future addition of more protocols to the system without obstructing the existing modules’ functionality.

B. Protocols

1) *ZWave*: is a wireless connectivity protocol that enables the connection between smart sensors and devices creating a network [13]. All ZWave devices interlink together wirelessly generating a mesh network as depicted in Fig. 3. The ZWave protocol uses radio waves with a dedicated frequency depending on each country’s legislation. Moreover, each device consists of a repeater that is capable of receiving and sending network data and information.

The main node used to create the ZWave network in this paper’s architecture is a USB stick which is plugged in the RPi. The stick is paired to all the sensors manually. Regarding the software, multiple projects already exist based on the C++ OpenZWave library. In this case, the open access standalone application 'zwave2mqtt' [14] was chosen based on the required functionality, which was to post data and receive commands through an Mqtt broker. It is installed as a startup service through docker-compose and is set up through a browser GUI.

Fig. 3. ZWave mesh network

2) *ZigBee*: is a protocol based on the IEEE's 802.15.4 network standard [15]. It is deployed in a mesh network in a similar manner to ZWave [16]. ZigBee operates on the 2.4GHz frequency band and its range is up to 20 meters for indoor spaces and up to 300 meters outdoors [15].

In the experiments, a ZigBee stick is plugged in the RPi and is manually paired to all sensors. The software used for maintaining the network is the headless version of deCONZ [17]. The software used to publish all ZigBee data to the MQTT broker is a python service which uses the "requests" library to fetch data from deCONZ's API and the "paho-MQTT" library to publish the data to the broker after they are mapped to the appropriate topics.

3) *ModBus*: is a transmitting protocol that is used to send information over serial lines among electronic devices [18]. The most widely used ModBus is RTU over RS485 [19].

Fig. 4. Energy smart meter chain connection

In the experiments, 3 to 4 ModBus energy analyzers were deployed per room. Since the topology allowed it, they were connected to the RPi gateway through a daisy chained RS485-to-USB adapter as depicted in Fig. 4. The software used to

publish the ModBus data to the MQTT broker is a Python service using the "pymodbus" library.

C. Services

1) *Mqtt2Bms* (Fig. 1): is a service in charge of subscribing to all topics in the broker and temporarily storing all incoming data in buffers. The data are posted to the BMS server through a secure, encrypted java-based API in configurable time intervals depending on the desirable time resolution. The service's functionality is not interrupted by any of the other sub-modules to ensure continuous monitoring and data retrieval. The mappings are used to link all data types to the final data frame that is posted to the BMS server and are the only part of the service that needs to be modified for adding new protocols to the system.

2) *Server MQTT Broker* (Fig. 1): This MQTT broker is hosted on a server with known and static IP configuration. Its purpose is to distribute actions produced by the BMS server to all gateways without the need of knowing each gateway's IP. Gateways can subscribe to their unique topics to receive commands using authentication to increase security. In the context of this paper's experiments, this server was hosted in a separate computer, but alternatively it can be integrated to the BMS system.

3) *ActionSync* (Fig. 1): is a python service utilized by all gateways to redirect the actions produced by the BMS system to the gateway's corresponding actuator software. The service subscribes to all the server's action topics and publishes the actions to the gateway's broker. Additionally, it translates the messages to the appropriate format, if needed. In the experiments, actions were tested for the ZWave protocol. The "zwave2mqtt" software specifies topics that are solely for receiving commands from any sensors with available actions.

D. Actions

To achieve energy savings through a BMS system, an Artificial Intelligence (AI) application must exist as described in the work of [20]. The objective of a BMS AI application

Fig. 5. Actions conceptual Architecture

is to change the electric usage towards energy savings while

preserving comfortable indoor conditions for the users. All the suggested actions are occupancy based and are decided through an optimization process.

The AI retrieves the current indoor conditions, occupancy, energy consumption, devices' states and other available information from the installed sensors and devices (Fig. 5). Subsequently, based on the functionality and parameters of the selected AI optimization algorithm (e.g., genetic algorithm, particle swan, simulated annealing), the BMS AI decides the next suggested energy saving actions to be applied to the BMS, based on pre-defined selected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The minimum number of KPIs needed for the optimization process are thermal comfort, visual comfort, savings and occupancy. Subsequently, those actions are sent from the BMS to the actuators and are applied to the BMS from the M2M IoT system. Data is managed and saved into a unique BMS system, as a result the BMS facilitates energy and environmental conditions reporting, while leading to better optimization processes and energy savings.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

TABLE I
SENSORS AND DEVICES' INFORMATION

	Sensor device	Protocol	Number of sensors	Actions
1	door window	ZWave	3	None
2	motion sensor	ZWave	1	None
3	smart plug	ZWave	3	on/ off
4	thermostatic valve	ZWave	1	on/off, set temperature
5	Carbon dioxide	ZWave	1	None
6	Temperature and humidity	ZigBee	1	None
7	Energy Analyzer	ModBus	3	None

The suggested IoT M2M architecture was tested in 4 different rooms, each one equipped with a single gateway. The number and type of sensors and devices that were installed in each room are presented in Table I.

Sensors and devices from different protocols were selected (i.e., ZWave, ZigBee, ModBus) to cover both energy consumption, indoor environmental conditions, occupancy, assets' status (e.g. windows) and optimize their use.

A floor plan sensor installation example is depicted in Fig. 6. The door window sensors are installed over each window to detect the window state (i.e., open/close). A thermostatic valve is placed on the radiator to monitor the radiator temperature and control its temperature and state (i.e., open/close). A motion sensor was installed to detect motion in the room. Temperature and CO_2 sensors are used to monitor indoor conditions. Moreover, an energy analyzer (smart meter) chain was installed to monitor the rooms' electric load. Finally, a RPi 4 was used as a gateway.

Fig. 6. Sensors network example

A. RPi Metrics

Stress tests were carried out to ensure that the gateways are operating normally, while the whole system is online. The monitored values include CPU usage and temperature, VRAM usage, network usage, disk usage, etc. An example of the daily RPi core temperature monitoring is depicted in Fig. 7. It may be observed that the RPi's average daily temperature is approximately $65^{\circ}C$. This temperature is considered efficient as it is around the RPi safe temperature cap.

Fig. 7. RPi temperature daily test

High levels of CPU usage may shorten the RPi's life span, therefore the CPU is continuously monitored. The average CPU usage while all processes are running is 48% (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. RPi CPU usage daily test

B. Monitoring results

In this sub-section selected daily results will be presented to demonstrate the systems' functionality. In this paper, Carlo

Gavazzi [21] energy analyzers using ModBus protocol were used to monitor energy consumption. As it may be observed in Fig. 9 the service responsible for collecting the monitored data from the analyzers' worked as intended. Energy consumption was retrieved among other variables in a predefined time resolution.

Fig. 9. Smart meter daily monitoring using ModBus protocol

In Fig. 10 the retrieved data from the motion sensor are depicted. The motion sensor reports a value equal to one if it detects any movement, else it reports zero.

Fig. 10. Motion sensor daily monitoring using ZWave protocol

In Fig. 11 the retrieved temperature data from the door-window sensor, the motion sensor, and the ZigBee temperature and humidity sensor are depicted. It may be observed how the door-window sensor and the ZigBee temperature sensor have a similar but shifted pattern. On the other hand, the temperature pattern reported from the motion sensor is different as the sensor is placed over an open door (Fig. 6).

Fig. 11. Temperature daily monitoring using ZWave and ZigBee protocol

C. Actions

The published actions result in changing the building's devices' state if the BMS AI reports new states. In Fig. 12 an example of a building's transition from a current devices' state to a next is presented. It may be observed that some

Fig. 12. Actions example

states remain the same, while others change based on available control actions (e.g., light dimming, thermal adjustment, on/off).

In Fig. 13 an example of the AI process is depicted. Initially, the current state is retrieved from the sensors and devices. Subsequently, the KPIs are estimated and along with the current occupancy, the BMS AI generates the decision-controls. In the example, the thermal comfort is neutral and the room has no occupancy, as a result the produced controls are: close device 5 and set the Heating Ventilation And Air conditioning (HVAC) to 25 °C. As it may be observed, the next state indicates that all the controls were successfully applied to the system. Moreover, the system's decision results in 9.68% savings.

Fig. 13. AI decisions example

CONCLUSIONS

There is no unique agreed-upon IoT M2M architecture. Each architecture differs based on its complexity, number of layers, number of sensors, and use-cases. Nevertheless, a basic IoT architecture must preserve interoperability and interlink with multiple protocols. Within this context, in this paper, a

practical basis for a system that is capable to link various communication technologies is suggested.

The Key objective of the system is to include all the required functionalities in an autonomous gateway and easily connect all gateways to the BMS systems'. Additionally, multiple sensor technologies are robustly included in each gateway's network so that the system can be modified and expanded to include new technologies. The proposed system was thoroughly tested and during the experiments, it is observed that the system is operating without errors.

In the future, more connectivity protocols, like a weather station operating on Wi-Fi, and a M-bus protocol will be added to the system. Moreover, the Mqtt server will be integrated into the BMS. Finally, long-term monitoring and overall system improvement will be performed.

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